

No effect of the Penalty Point System on road traffic accident mortality among men with a high socioeconomic status in Spain

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ABSTRACT

The purpose of this study was to assess the effect of the Penalty Point System (PPS) on road traffic accident mortality by gender and socioeconomic status. We conducted a nationwide prospective study covering adult people living in Spain on November 2001. They were followed up until 30 Nov 2007 to determine vital status and cause of death. An interrupted time-series analysis was used to assess whether PPS (explanatory variable) had both immediate and long-term effect on the rates of road traffic accident mortality (RTAMs) separately by gender. Subjects were classified by socioeconomic status (low and high) using two indicators: educational attainment (up to lower secondary education; upper secondary education or more) and occupation (manual and non-manual workers). We performed several segmented Poisson regression models, controlling for trend, seasonality, 2004 road safety measures and fuel consumption as proxy for traffic exposure. Among men, we found a decrease on the RTAMs immediately after PPS in those with low educational level (16.2 %, IC95 %: 6.1 %–25.2 %) and manual workers (16.3 %, IC95 %: 2.8 %–27.8 %), and a non-significant increase among those with high education level and non-manual workers (6.2 % and 1.8 %). Among women, there were no significant differences in the immediate effect of PPS by socioeconomic status. We did not identify significant trend changes between pre-PPS and post-PPS periods in any socioeconomic group. In a context of downward trend of traffic mortality, the PPS implementation led to an immediate reduction on death rates only among men with a low socioeconomic status.

1. Introduction

The Penalty Point System (PPS) has been incorporated in road safety legislations of middle- and high-income countries on all continents, although its expansion has been particularly notable in Europe. A recent worldwide meta-analysis showed that the implementation of this strategy was associated with 15 %–20 % reductions in accidents, fatalities and injuries (Castillo-Manzano and Castro-Nuno, ~ 2012). Previous studies have shown that road traffic accidents (RTA) mortality is higher among people with low socioeconomic status (Borrell et

al., 2005; Cubbin et al., 2000a; Spoerri et al., 2011; Steenland et al., 2003; Whitlock et al., 2003). However, so far, there are no studies that have evaluated the impact of the PPS in any country or region on different socio-economic groups. The PPS is a measure recommended by international institutions due to its ability to identify drivers who repeatedly commit offences, and also because it is considered a fairer strategy than economic fines (it affects all drivers equally regardless of their purchasing power) (ETSC, 2008; Van Schagen and Machata, 2012). In Spain, the PPS came into effect on July 1, 2006. From that point on, all drivers had an initial credit of 12 points on their license (8 points for novices). If drivers with more than three years of experience do not lose points in three consecutive years, they will get a bonus of 2 more points. After another three years with no offenses, they will add another point, until achieving the maximum of points allowed (15 points). Novice drivers or those who have obtained their license again after having been suspended, will have 12 points after 2 years without offences. They can also get the bonus of up to 15 points following the same process as any other driver. The points could be deducted depending on the traffic offence committed, from a minimum of 2 points (e.g. driving without headlights when required, driving vehicles that have systems to evade the surveillance of traffic officers or to detect speed cameras, etc.) to a maximum of 6 points (e.g. driving with a blood alcohol content >0.50 mg/l, driving under the influence of other psychoactive drugs, speeding >50 % of the maximum authorized speed, reckless driving and refusing analysis of psychoactive drugs) (DGT, 2020). When a driver loses all points, the consequence is the suspension of the license for 6 months (3 months for professional drivers). Additionally, to recover the driving license, the sanctioned driver must attend an awareness and road re-education training and pass an exam.

The behavioral factors collectively represent the principal cause of 60 % RTA and contribute to the causation of 95 % of these accidents (Petridou and Moustaki, 2000). The main driver-dependent risk factors associated with the risk of causing a collision are sleepiness, inappropriate speed, and driving under the influence of alcohol (Lardelli-Claret et al., 2003), precisely some of the infractions that lead to a greatest loss of points in the PPS. Abundant studies have shown that less educated and low-occupation population groups show higher prevalence of driving under the influence (Oksanen et al., 2015), inappropriate speed (Chen et al., 2010b; Shinar et al., 2001), using seat belts (Babio and Daponte-Codina, 2006; Foss et al., 1994; Shinar et al., 2001), wearing helmet (Babio and Daponte-Codina, 2006) and using child restraint system (Babio and Daponte-Codina, 2006; Keay et al., 2013). In turn, the most disadvantaged socio-economic groups also have higher risk of injury morbidity and mortality (Braver, 2003; Chen et al., 2010a; Cubbin et al., 2000a, b; Fleury et al., 2010; Harper et al., 2015; Howard et al., 2000; Spoerri et al., 2011; Steenland et al., 2003). Due to the fact that human factors associated to traffic accidents are influenced by socioeconomic position (SEP), it is plausible that the impact of the PPS on RTA mortality will differ across SEP groups.

As the objective of the PPS is to deter drivers from committing offences, the assessment of this coercive measure should be carried out by quantifying the reduction of the most serious risk behaviors or, as has normally been done so far, the reduction of the number of occupants/ pedestrians killed or wounded since its implementation. In Spain, previous studies have observed a 11 %-14.5 % reduction in overall deaths from RTA (Castillo-Manzano et al., 2010; Castillo-Manzano and Castro-Nuno, ~ 2012; Izquierdo et al., 2011; Novoa et al., 2010; Pulido et al., 2010), similar to the reductions observed in serious injuries, but much higher than among other accident victims (those with minor injuries or

unharmed), demonstrating that the PPS is very effective penalizing especially serious infractions (Novoa et al., 2010).

However, there are no previous studies that have measured the differential effect of the PPS among different SEP groups. One reason for this is that PPS and other legislative measures have been evaluated using police-based data. Databases of this nature allow stratification by age, gender, type of user, vehicle characteristics and several crash circumstances (type of road or collision, time, atmospheric conditions, etc.) but do not usually include SEP indicators. As with other coercive measures aimed at reducing exposure to negative health factors, such as smoke free legislation (Federico et al., 2012; Regidor et al., 2015), one of the key elements in terms of public health assessment is whether these population-based interventions increase or reduce existing inequalities.

Thus, the aim of this study was to assess the impact of the PPS, introduced in Spain on July 1, 2006, on road traffic accident mortality by socioeconomic position. In addition, we also assessed whether the PPS had both an immediate and long-term impact on different socioeconomic groups. Our hypothesis was that the PPS had a more favorable impact in terms of reducing road accident mortality in low socioeconomic groups than in high socioeconomic groups.

2. Material and methods

2.1. Data source

Data are extracted from the National Longitudinal Mortality Study based on the 2001 Census (INE, 2016), a closed cohort which included all people residing in Spain on November 1, 2001 (40,847,371), who were followed until 31 December 2011 to determine vital status and cause of death. The final database was developed by the National Institute of Statistics (INE) who linked individual records from the Census with the population and mortality registries using common identifiers. Some 1.7% could not be found and they were excluded from the follow-up cohort. Additionally, the contribution of 395,975 subjects to the risk of death was censored because they had moved abroad and information could not be obtained thereafter. We compared sociodemographic characteristics between excluded/censored and included subjects in the cohort and statistical differences were not found.

2.2. Variables

The outcome was the monthly number of deaths from traffic injuries, and was counted according with International Classification of Diseases, 10th Edition (ICD-10). Within the section “land transport accidents” (V01-V89) we selected the following codes: V01-V06(.1,.9), V10-V18 (.4,.5,.9), V19(.4,.5,.6,.9), V20-V28(.4,.5,.9), V29(.4,.5,.6,.9), V30-V38 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V39(.4,.5,.6,.9), V40-V48(.5,.6,.7,.9), V49(.4,.5,.6,.9), V50-V58(.5,.6,.7,.9), V59(.5,.6,.9), V60-V68(.5,.6,.7,.9), V39 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V70-V78(.5,.6,.7,.9), V79(.4,.5,.6,.9), V81,V82(.1,.9), V83– 86(.0–.3), V87 and V89 (.2,.3). This definition excludes RTA deaths outside public roads, “while boarding or alighting to vehicle” (codified with a fourth digit “.0” between V10 and V79) and those injured in non-traffic accidents (codified with digits “.1”, “.2” and “.3” between V10 and V79) as recommended by international organizations (Perez et al., 2014).

The outcome was assessed separately for men and women and stratified by SEP. Two SEP indicators were used, educational attainment and occupational status. The first refers to the highest education level completed and was grouped into two categories (low and high) according to International Standard Classification of Education (ISCED) (UNESCO Institute of Statistics, 2018): \leq lower secondary education (ISCED-levels 0–2) and \geq upper secondary education (ISCED-levels 3–8). Occupational status was based on specific occupation of people employed in the week preceding the interview and grouped into manual and non-manual workers.

The PPS implementation was included as a dummy variable with “zero value” before the implementation (January 2002-June 2006), and “one” after the implementation (July 2006-November 2007). Despite having a longer time series, the impact of the PPS were assessed until 2007 to avoid confounding of the Reform of Spanish Criminal Code of 1 December 2007 (Novoa et al., 2011) and the Economic Crisis beginning in 2008 (Regidor et al., 2016).

In 2003, the Spanish government established road safety as a political priority (Novoa et al., 2011). Firstly, a package of Road Safety Special Measures during 2004–2005 (RSM-2004) was implemented to ensure rapid results. These measures were: a) to create a Spanish Road Safety Observatory; b) to strengthen the Higher Council for Road Safety; c) to increase traffic officers and technological surveillance devices (especially radars); d) to implement new information campaigns by risk groups; e) to review the training model, incorporating more safety-related contents and behaviors in the tests; and f) to develop a common guideline for the development of local road safety plans based on the number of inhabitants that includes analysis of the accident rate (DGT, 2006). These measures had a strong impact on reducing the accidentally (Novoa et al., 2011), therefore, another dummy covariate was created to control for the effect of the RSM-2004. The age as time-varying (in each calendar-month of follow up) and seasonality were also considered. Finally, fuel consumption per inhabitant according to region of residence was assessed as a proxy of the traffic exposure.

2.3. Statistical analysis

To describe mortality time series, we calculated monthly agestandardized rates of road traffic accident mortality (sRTAMs) per 100 000 person-years between January 2002 and November 2007 across different socioeconomic groups using weights from 2013 European Standard Population. We also compared overall RTA death rates in three different separate periods based on the implementation dates of the RSM-2004 and the PPS: Pre-RSM-2004 (January 2002-December 2003), Pre-PPS (January 2004-June 2006), and Post-PPS (July 2006-November 2007).

Consequently, a segmented Poisson regression analysis was used to assess whether the intervention (PPS) had both immediate and longterm effect on outcome (RTA mortality). We performed an intervention model that estimated level and slope changes (Bernal et al., 2017), adjusting for age, fuel consumption, pre-intervention linear time trend and seasonality through Fourier terms. The model can be summarized as follows: $\ln(Y_t) = \beta_0 + \beta_1 T + \beta_2 X_t + \beta_3 T X_t + \beta_4 X_t + \beta_5 T X_t + \sum_j (\beta_6 j Z_{jt}) + e_t$, where Y_t is the outcome at time t , T the months elapsed since the start of the study, X_t is a dummy variable for RSM-2004 and PPS that indicate the pre-intervention period ($X = 0$) and the post-intervention period ($X = 1$) and Z refers to others adjustment co-variables (age and fuel consumption). In this segmented regression, β coefficients are interpreted as follows: β_0 represents the baseline level at $T = 0$, β_1 estimates the monthly change in the outcome in Pre-RSM-2004, β_2 is the level change

in outcome immediately after RSM-2004, β_3 is the difference in outcome trends between Pre-PPS and Pre-RSM-2004, β_4 estimates the level change in the outcome immediately after PPS and β_5 the difference in outcome trends between Post-PPS and Pre-PPS. Finally, ϵ represents the random variability not explained by the model. Person-moths at risk was included in the models as an offset variable.

Separate models were built for different socioeconomic groups in both men and women. Different study populations by age and employment status were selected according to the SEP indicator studied. Thus, when educational attainment was assessed, a minimum age of 25 at Census interview was established (age of entry into the cohort) to minimize the number of individuals whose educational attainment was not the same as at baseline assuming that from that age onward very few people will improve their educational level (Harper et al., 2015). On the other hand, when differences between manual and non-manual workers were assessed only employed population at working age (16– 64 years) was analyzed.

To facilitate the interpretation, β regression coefficients for level and trend changes were transformed in percentage changes (PC) and monthly percentage changes (MPC) as $100 \cdot [\exp(\beta) - 1]$. We computed 95 % confidence intervals (CI) using the standard error (SE) of β as follows: $100 \cdot [\exp(\beta \pm 1.96SE) - 1]$. Autocorrelation was tested using Durbin-Watson statistic (values close to 2 indicates no autocorrelation) and overdispersion was tested using a scale parameter estimated by the Pearson chi-square statistic divided by the residual degrees of freedom (values close to 1 indicates no overdispersion). Finally, we have performed a sensitivity analysis with Negative Binomial regression models since the goodness-of-fit indicators of the Poisson models usually reflect over-dispersion, which is common for count data. Analyses were performed with Stata 14.0 (Stata Corporation, College Station, Texas).

2.4. Ethics approval

This study was approved by the Institutional Review Board of the INE. Approval by the Ethics Committee was not required since the 2001 Census database did not include variables allowing personal identification.

3. Results

Between January 2002 and November 2007, there were 16 575 RTA fatalities among those who were ≥ 25 years old and 9 557 deaths among employees at age 16– 64. Between 76.3 % and 87.6 % occurred in men and women, respectively. The distribution of RTA fatalities by educational and occupation status was similar to that of Spanish population. Thus, 75.8 % of deaths at age ≥ 25 corresponded to people that had completed \leq lower secondary education in 2001 and 62.6 % of deaths among employees aged 16– 64 corresponded to manual workers (75.1 % and 66.8 %, respectively, among men, and 78 % and 32.5 % among women). The sRTAM at age ≥ 25 was 10.2 per 100 000 personyears at risk (CI 95 %: 10.1– 10.4) and was much higher among men than in women (16.4 and 4.6, respectively), whereas sRTAM among employees at age 16– 64 was 13.2 (CI95 %: 13.0–13.5), and also remained higher among men than women (18.8 and 4.0).

3.1. Road traffic accident mortality rates by socioeconomic position before and after Penalty Point System by gender

Table 1 shows the number of RTA deaths, person-years at risk and sRTAMs before and after the implementation of the PPS. In Spain, RTA mortality was already substantially reduced in the second period (after RSM-2004). Among men, sRTAMs decreased by 16 % in people aged ≥ 25 years and 32 % in the employed population within working age (16– 64), although these reductions were greater among people in high socioeconomic positions. In the post-intervention period (after PPS) the reductions were greater only among low education group (22 % Vs. 15 %). Among women, the highest RTA mortality reductions were observed in non-manual workers group after RSM-2004. However, after PPS, a higher mortality reduction was observed among women with high educational level.

3.2. Level and trend changes in RTA mortality after the PPS implementation

Table 2 shows the results from impact models of the PPS on RTA mortality. Overall, a significant linear downward trend during the preintervention period, just after the implementation of RSM-2004, was observed both in men and women across all SEP groups. Regarding the immediate level change after PPS, a strong decrease of RTA mortality among men was observed immediately after the implementation of the PPS in both low-SEP groups: 16.2 % (CI95 %: 6.1 %–25.2 %) in the low education group and 16.3 % (CI95 %: 2.8 %–27.8 %) among manual workers. In both high socioeconomic groups, a slight immediate increase was observed (6.2 % and 1.8 %, $p > 0.05$) (see Fig. 1). Among women, we observed an immediate increase after the PPS, that was higher among high socioeconomic group. However, confidence intervals were wide ($p > 0.05$). Regarding trend changes after PPS, in both men and women the implementation of PPS did not result in a trend change on RTA mortality across different SEP groups ($p > 0.05$). However, among men the magnitude of change was much smaller than in women. Linear post-PPS trends were downwards among all socioeconomic groups, except in men with a low occupation, although the sign of trend change in men was positive (post-PPS trend was less steep) and negative in women (post-PPS trend was steeper). The results obtained through the Negative Binomial regression analysis were similar to those obtained with the Poisson regression analysis (Supplementary Table 1).

4. Discussion

Before the introduction of the PPS in Spain, the magnitude of road traffic accident mortality showed a downward trend in all socioeconomic groups. This downward trend was steeper in high-SEP groups (\geq upper secondary education and non-manual workers). For men, the introduction of the PPS had a strong and favorable immediate effect in low-SEP groups (\leq lower secondary education and manual workers), which was not observed among men in high-SEP. For women, the findings did not allow to establish a differential effect of the PPS according to socioeconomic position, although the immediate effect of PPS on road accident mortality was less unfavorable among low socioeconomic groups. Despite the immediate positive effects in low SEP men, no trend changes were observed after the implementation of the PPS by SEP, RTA mortality continued to show a decreasing trend in all socioeconomic groups, except in males manual workers.

The PPS is a legislative measure that was complementary to traditional police enforcement and affects, as a rule, to all drivers regardless of socioeconomic position (Van Schagen and Machata, 2012). However, the differences found in PPS immediate effect on RTA mortality rates in low and high SEP groups may be explained from different perspectives.

Firstly, several studies have found a higher risk of RTA injury among people with low educational and occupational status (Borrell et al., 2005; Cubbin et al., 2000a; Spoerri et al., 2011; Steenland et al., 2003; Whitlock et al., 2003). In a study by Whitlock et al., authors observed a three-fold higher risk among subjects in the lowest occupational status group compared to subjects in the highest group. Similar results were found by Steenland et al. when assessing the association between occupational status and motor vehicles deaths (Steenland et al., 2003). Other studies also found an increased risk (between 20 %–53 %) of RTA deaths among people with low education compared to people with high educational attainment (Borrell et al., 2005; Cubbin et al., 2000a; Spoerri et al., 2011). Furthermore, drivers from low socioeconomic areas also showed a risk increased of crash-related hospitalization compared to drivers from high socioeconomic areas (Chen et al., 2010a), and SEP is also an important determinant of non-fatal outcome after injury and crash severity (Hasselberg et al., 2005; Kruithof et al., 2017). The reasons why people with low SEP had a higher risk of RTA can be found in their driving behaviors. In fact, using seat belts and driving at or below the speed limit increases with education and driving under the influence of psychoactive drugs and the non-use of child restraint systems are associated with low education and low household income (Chen and Jou, 2018; Keay et al., 2013; Oksanen et al., 2015; Shinar et al., 2001). Thus, given these results and the fact that the PPS System penalizes especially infractions directly related to accident risk (such as the abovementioned), the greater immediate impact of the measure in the low socioeconomic group we observed in our study was somehow expected.

Secondly, the deterrent effect of the PPS has been demonstrated in some studies (Sagberg and Ingebrigtsen, 2018). The implementation of PPS involves an additional punishment (the driving license suspension) when all points are lost or a threshold is reached. Therefore, people with a low SEP might be more concerned about license revocation than people with better socioeconomic position, especially just before and after the new legislation when the level of uncertainty about its application is higher. Another possible reason is that a higher proportion of the low SEP group might work in the transportation sector and, thus, need to drive for a living.

Thirdly, the implementation of PPS was accompanied by an important media campaign that started months before the law was applied. Other studies have already described that highly educated people are better at distilling important health information from public messages and thereby better in making healthy choices (Galobardes et al., 2006). Therefore, this could make people with a high education level improved their driving behaviors, even before the application of the law, reducing especially those typified with greater loss of points. This may explain why the PPS did not have an immediate effect among high SEP groups.

To the best of our knowledge, this is the first study that analyzes the effect of PPS by SEP. According to Haddon matrix (Haddon, 1968), the PPS is a legislative measure that could be placed within the public policies that prevent accidents (pre-accident phase) in the social environment (Villalbi and Perez, 2006). However, in view of the results of this study, the PPS can also be considered a measure that reduces the social inequalities between high- and low-level socioeconomic groups at least in the immediate impact of fatal injuries.

4.1. Comparison with previous studies

To our knowledge this is the first study that assessed the impact of the PPS on RTA mortality across socioeconomic groups. However, some general remarks should not be missing from this article. The studies that assessed the effectiveness of the PPS separately in men and women showed that the PPS led to a significant reduction in RTA deaths only among males (Farchi et al., 2007; Novoa et al., 2010). This finding was also found in this study, in which we observed an immediate and significant decrease in mortality of 10.9 % (IC95 %: 1.2 %–19.7 %) among males aged ≥ 25 years, without affecting the downward trend after 2004 (MPC diff 0.4; IC 95 %: -0.5, 1.3). In Spain, with the implementation of the package of RSM-2004, the favorable change in the trend on RTA mortality among women was much larger than in men (Novoa et al., 2011). Some authors explain this difference by the higher willingness for behavior change and a safer driving behavior among women, even as a passenger (Laapotti and Keskinen, 1998; Laapotti et al., 2003; Nazif-Munoz and Blank-Gomel, 2017; Shinar et al., 2001). With the implementation of the PPS, only two and a half years after the RSM-2004, there was probably room for further mortality decrease in men, but not in women (Novoa et al., 2011).

On the other hand, this approach consisting on assessing the immediate and long-term effect of the PPS across socioeconomic groups has already been applied in the evaluation of other coercive measures, for example, the smoke-free legislations (Federico et al., 2012; Regidor et al., 2015). In Spain, after the introduction of the law, the smoking cessation (using quit ratio) only increased in women with a low education level. The ban altered preexisting trends, except among men with high education (Regidor et al., 2015). Therefore, our results represent another example of how this type of coercive laws do not have a clear immediate effect on subjects with a high educational level

4.2. Strengths and limitations

This study is based on one of the largest population cohorts, composed of the entire resident population in Spain at the end of 2001. To our knowledge, this is the first study to assess the impact of the PPS on RTA mortality across socioeconomic groups. Data on educational level and type of occupation are not frequently available in police databases, which have been used by all previous evaluation studies. Moreover, the findings were consistent using two SEP indicators. The cohort follow-up had very few losses, by contrast with other similar population cohorts, therefore individual-level characteristics did not change between the pre- and post-PPS period, avoiding selection biases. In the case of selection of deaths, we decided not to include fatalities off public roads, while boarding or alighting to vehicle and people injured in non-traffic accidents in order to analyze fatalities in public roads, the target scenarios of PPS.

Some studies on factors associated with highway safety use random intercept models to account for unobserved heterogeneity across observations (Meng et al., 2020; Tang et al., 2019). The Poisson and the negative binomial regression models do not account for unobserved heterogeneity. This means that there are unobserved factors that exert some influence on the variability related to the response variable. In order to consider unobserved heterogeneity, the regression parameters β considered as having variations across observations must be treated as random and not modelled as having fixed-effects. Therefore, we have estimated random parameters Poisson and negative binomial models where the constant term is assumed to be random across geographic areas (Tang et al., 2019). The results hardly vary with respect to the results obtained in the models with fixed effects (Supplementary Tables 2 and 3).

Our study has some drawbacks, which should be noted. SEP was measured at baseline. People are likely to change their educational level or occupational status during a 7-year-follow-up. However, in the case of the education achievement, people aged 25 years and over were selected to minimize this bias, assuming that from that age the likelihood of education level improvement is very low. Like other studies that evaluated nationwide public measures, no comparison group was available. However, single-group interrupted time series designs have important strengths, particularly because they allow adjusting by time trend, seasonality, previous interventions and other measured ecological confounding factors. We were unable to stratify our results by type of road user (driver, passenger, pedestrian) because of a misclassification of the ICD 10 codes that affected 25 % of the sample.

5. Conclusions

This is the first study that has assessed the effect of the Penalty Point System on road accident mortality in different socioeconomic groups. Our findings suggest that the introduction of the Penalty Point System in Spain had a strong and favorable immediate effect among men with a low education and occupation status in the context of a downward trend during the first decade of the 21st century. However, this legislation did not represent a change in the pre-intervention trend which had been clearly downward since the implementation of the large package of road safety measures implemented in 2004. Among women, the findings do not allow to establish a differential effect of the PPS according to socioeconomic position.

Although the application of the Penalty Point System is similar in different countries, caution should be exercised in extrapolating the results found to other socioeconomic regions since the effectiveness of this coercive measure depends on the level of enforcement that each country applies against risky driving behaviors. Future studies should investigate the effect of the PPS on different road users according to their socioeconomic position, especially on drivers (the main target of the PPS), and with a longer post-intervention follow-up time that allows for a more adequate assessment of the long-term effect of the PPS.

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Table 1Number of deaths^a, person-years at risk and age-standardized rates of road traffic accident before and after Penalty Point System, by gender and socioeconomic position. Spanish Census Cohort, 2002–2007.

	Pre-intervention (period 1)				Pre-intervention (period 2)				Post-intervention (period 3)			
	Deaths	Person-years at risk	sRTAM	(95 % CI)	Deaths	Person-years at risk	sRTAM	(95 % CI)	Deaths	Person-years at risk	sRTAM	(95 % CI)
<i>Men</i>												
Educational attainment^a												
≤Lower secondary	3841	17782189	21,7	(21,0 22,4)	3947	21360400	18,8	(18,2 19,4)	1709	11614409	14,6	(14,0 15,2)
≥Upper secondary	1272	9511907	14,0	(13,3 14,7)	1231	11757378	11,1	(10,5 11,7)	586	6541287	9,4	(8,8 10,1)
Population aged ≥ 25	5145	27438002	19,1	(18,6 19,6)	5200	33267396	16,0	(15,6 16,4)	2306	18225802	12,7	(12,2 13,2)
Occupation^b												
Manual workers	2503	10596435	24,8	(23,9 25,8)	2493	12969487	20,6	(19,8 21,4)	1099	7094752	16,9	(16,0 17,7)
Non-manual workers	1255	8895956	17,8	(17,0 18,6)	1204	10922476	12,0	(11,4 12,6)	564	6004496	10,0	(9,2 10,7)
Employed population aged 16–64	3758	19492391	21,8	(21,2 22,4)	3697	23891963	14,8	(14,3 15,3)	1663	13099247	14,3	(13,7 14,9)
<i>Women</i>												
Educational attainment^a												
≤Lower secondary	1227	20386941	5,5	(5,2 5,9)	1252	24656646	4,6	(4,3 4,9)	583	13509694	3,9	(3,5 4,2)
≥Upper secondary	368	9038496	4,7	(4,3 5,1)	336	11243750	4,0	(3,6 4,3)	133	6292441	2,8	(2,5 3,2)
Population aged ≥ 25	1609	29682720	5,4	(5,2 5,7)	1596	36158384	4,4	(4,2 4,6)	719	19923409	3,6	(3,3 3,8)
Occupation^b												
Manual workers	187	3245339	6,1	(5,3 6,9)	154	3985088	5,0	(4,4 5,6)	77	2185948	3,8	(3,1 4,6)
Non-manual workers	388	8801583	5,0	(4,6 5,5)	338	10905733	3,6	(3,3 4,0)	141	6066118	2,6	(2,2 3,0)
Employed population aged 16–64	575	12046922	5,3	(4,9 5,7)	492	14890821	3,3	(3,0 3,6)	218	8252065	3,0	(2,7 3,4)

sRTAM: Age-standardized rates of road traffic accident per 100,000 person-years using the weights of the 2013 European Standard Population; 95 % CI: Confidence interval at 95 %.

Pre-intervention (period 1): Before the implementation of a large package of Road Safety Measures during 2004 (from January 2002 to December 2003); **Pre-intervention (period 2):** After the implementation of a package of Road Safety Measures during 2004 and before the Penalty Point System (from January 2004 to June 2006); **Post-intervention (period 3):** after the Penalty Point System (from 1 July 2006 to 30 November 2007).^a ICD-10 codes: V01-V06 (.1,.9), V10-V18 (.4,.5,.9), V19 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V20-V28 (.4,.5,.9), V29 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V30-V38 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V39 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V40-V48 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V49 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V50-V58 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V59 (.5,.6,.9), V60-V68 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V39 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V70-V78 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V79 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V81, V82 (.1,.9), V83–86 (.0–.3), V87, V89.^a Referred to road fatalities in population aged ≥ 25.^b Referred to road fatalities in population aged 16–64.

Table 2

Level and trend changes on road accident mortality risk from segmented regression models after implementation of Road Safety Measures 2004 and the Penalty Point System (July 1, 2006) in Spain. Spanish Census Cohort, 2002–2007.

	Baseline trend			Road Safety Measures during 2004						Penalty Point System					
				Level change			Linear trend change			Level change			Linear trend change		
	MPC	95 % CI		PC	95 % CI		MPC diff	95 % CI		PC	95 % CI		MPC diff	95 % CI	
<i>Men</i>															
Educational attainment^a															
≤ Lower Secondary	-0,4	-0,8	0,1	-4,4	-12,6	4,6	-0,1	-0,7	0,4	-16,2	-25,2	-6,1	0,5	-0,5	1,4
≥ Upper Secondary	-0,3	-1,1	0,5	-4,4	-18,3	11,8	-0,7	-1,7	0,4	6,2	-12,7	29,3	0,3	-1,4	1,9
Population aged ≥ 25 years	-0,3	-0,8	0,1	-5,1	-12,6	3,0	-0,3	-0,9	0,2	-10,9	-19,7	-1,2	0,4	-0,5	1,3
Occupation^b															
Manual workers	0,2	-0,5	0,8	-11,4	-21,2	-0,4	-0,5	-1,2	0,3	-16,3	-27,8	-2,8	0,5	-0,7	1,8
Non-manual workers	0,2	-0,7	1,2	-8,3	-23,0	9,1	-0,9	-2,1	0,2	1,8	-18,1	26,5	0,1	-1,7	2,0
Employed population aged 16–64 years	0,0	-0,5	0,5	-9,6	-18,1	-0,2	-0,5	-1,1	0,1	-8,5	-19,0	3,5	0,4	-0,7	1,5
<i>Women</i>															
Educational attainment^a															
≤ Lower Secondary	-0,6	-1,4	0,3	-3,1	-17,8	14,3	-0,2	-1,3	0,9	2,2	-16,3	24,7	-0,9	-2,5	0,8
≥ Upper Secondary	-1,2	-2,7	0,4	11,4	-18,1	51,4	-0,8	-2,8	1,2	27,1	-15,6	91,4	-1,1	-4,6	2,4
Population aged ≥ 25 years	-0,8	-1,5	0,0	0,8	-12,7	16,5	-0,3	-1,2	0,7	7,8	-10,1	29,2	-1,0	-2,6	0,6

Models were adjusted by underline linear trend, age, seasonality and fuel consumption per capita.

Traffic deaths were selected using the following ICD-10 codes: V01-V06 (.1,.9), V10-V18 (.4,.5,.9), V19 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V20-V28 (.4,.5,.9), V29 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V30-V38 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V39 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V40-V48 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V49 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V50-V58 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V59 (.5,.6,.9), V60-V68 (.5,.6,.7,.9), V39 (.4,.5,.6,.9), V70-V78.

MPC: Monthly percentage change; **PC:** Percentage change; **MPC diff:** Difference in MPC between pre-intervention and post-intervention periods.

^a Referred to road fatalities in population aged ≥25.

^b Referred to road fatalities in population aged ≥16–64.